

SELF-HEALING COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: This paper discusses preliminary result obtained from novel ‘self-healing’ epoxy resin systems intended for use in composite materials. Composites are susceptible to a variety of matrix crack types, including delamination and transverse fracture, which can initiate catastrophic failure of the component, making repair or replacement necessary. Repair generally requires a gross intervention and is therefore impractical for small damages. Several self-healing technologies have been proposed, which allow small damages to be healed without gross intervention, but they mainly rely on delivery of liquid resin to the damage site, which introduces manufacturing difficulties. This paper presents a healing system, based on conventional epoxies, that is capable of regaining up to 70% of the original mechanical properties in fractured resin specimens; and to provide a visible reduction in damage area upon healing of composite panels. The implications of such a resin on manufacture of composites will be considered.

KEYWORDS: Self-healing, repair, fracture toughness, smart materials.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are particularly susceptible to impact damage and matrix cracking, which can lead to a substantial loss in mechanical properties. Unfortunately this damage is often very difficult to observe physically at the surface of the panel, a situation known as barely visible impact damage (BVID). This necessitates non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques in order to locate and quantify the extent of damage, meaning that such techniques as ultrasonic C-scanning and x-ray analysis must be employed. This is costly and time-consuming, which has led to interest in the development of a variety of smart sensors. Smart sensors are intended to provide a similar capability to the NDT techniques, in that they identify the damage and enable rectification work to be conducted. However, as they are embedded in the structure they can work in real-time and give online warnings of the damage state.

Having used either smart sensing or NDT techniques, it is necessary for the operator to decide whether to keep the situation under review or to conduct a repair. This is not necessarily a simple decision as composite repair techniques generally require gross intervention in order to rectify the problem. It is common therefore to keep small damages under review to determine whether they grow, at which point they can be rectified, or the component can be scrapped. However, if it were possible to intervene when the damage was small, it may be possible to maintain the damage state, preventing growth and maximising the performance of the component. With this in mind, techniques by which small damages can be repaired without necessitating large-scale intervention are desirable, and have been under investigation for around a decade. To date, these can be divided in to two main types, liquid resin techniques and modified resin techniques.

The majority of the published techniques are liquid resin techniques, and employ either capillary tubes or spherical capsules as storage vessels for liquid resin [1-5]. The occurrence of a fracture causes bleeding of the uncured resin contained within the vessel, which either then mixes with a liquid curing agent contained within neighbouring vessels, or reacts with a solid catalyst that is dispersed throughout the matrix. In this way, the liquid resin acts to re-bond fracture surfaces, thereby healing matrix cracks and allowing recovery of some load carrying capability.

These techniques are limited by their reliance on liquid resin delivery. A vessel of liquid resin must be incorporated into the composite material, and must fracture at the same time as the matrix. If capillary fibres [1,2] are used then fibre fracture is necessary for healing, but fibre fracture normally occurs substantially after the onset of matrix cracking, which is usually the first failure mechanism in a composite material. Therefore, these capillary fibres need to be able to fracture at low loads in order to achieve healing. This in effect results in a weakening of the composite structure in order to facilitate the healing step which is clearly undesirable. The incorporation of spherical vessels [3-5], which behave like voids within the matrix, could reduce the modulus of the composite and initiate crack formation at lower loads. Again, the decision to deliberately weaken the composite structure in order to obtain a healing capability seems undesirable. With both of these technologies, repeat healings can be performed, but only while liquid resin is present. It is therefore not routinely possible to know that such a system will reliably respond when required to do so. Another potential problem with the incorporation of fragile sealed capillaries or microcapsules, of diameter of 50 μm is the disruption of the fibre/resin architecture. Furthermore, capillaries are likely to fracture during manufacture.

A second approach to healing [6], employing a modified resin system, is to employ specially designed matrices containing a weak chemical bond which will preferentially break and reform on heating. Therefore, the matrix can be thermally repaired after fracture. This approach will require completely new matrix and manufacturing technologies, which can only be introduced over a longer term, after extensive verification studies. It is also yet to be proved that the materials have sufficient mechanical properties to make them attractive as replacement matrices in composite applications.

For the reasons outlined above, the need for alternative technologies was identified, and a solid-state healable system, based on conventional resin technology has been developed and patented [7]. This has been developed using a conventional epoxy resin system, and incorporating a soluble thermoplastic, which does not phase separate upon cure, but is not strongly bound to the epoxy resin chains. In essence this thermoplastic is free to move within the structure of the thermosetting matrix upon heating, and as such can diffuse across any fracture surfaces, bridging the fractures and restoring some of the mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Healing Matrix

The healing matrix system was produced using a base thermosetting resin consisting of Huntsman Araldite LY1556 and GY298 epoxy resins, cured with nadic methylene anhydride and Cognis Chemicals Capcure 3-800, a mercaptan terminated curing agent that, in this case, acts as an accelerator for the anhydride. The proportions of each component are given in

Table 1. Once blended, the resin was cured at 80°C for 4 hours, followed by a postcure at 130°C for 3 hours.

Table 1. Proportions of each constituent used in the blends

Constituent	Weight
LY1556	15 g
GY298	10 g
NMA	15.96 g
Capcure 3-800	5.95 g

To this blend was added a thermoplastic material that was selected to be highly compatible with the main constituent, LY1556, which is a Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol-A based resin. The selected thermoplastic was Poly Bisphenol-A-co-Epichlorohydrin (Sigma Aldrich 18,119-6). This was added to the resin in two proportions, of 10 wt% and 20 wt%, with the higher proportion being studied using compact tension testing, and the lower proportion being used to manufacture composites. It was found that this material was highly compatible with the resin system both before and after cure, and remained in solution throughout processing.

Resin Testing

Testing of the ability of the matrix to heal was carried out using compact tension testing, with samples being prepared according to BS13586:2000 [8], with the dimensions shown in Figure 1. Samples of the healing resin system were tested, alongside reference samples consisting of the resin blend only. The reference system was subjected to the same tests as the healing matrix to determine whether any healing effect was truly a result of the thermoplastic addition or could be ascribed to the resin itself.

Figure 1. Dimensions of the compact tension test specimens

Under test, these samples were fully fractured, with the two halves being immediately relocated and lightly clamped together before being heated over a range of temperatures, to assess the healing performance. The samples were then retested to check the healing efficiency. Samples were repeatedly healed and tested throughout the study, enabling an assessment of repeat healing to be conducted as well.

Composite Testing

Glass-fibre composites were produced using the resin system containing 10 wt% of the thermoplastic healing agent, using a vacuum assisted resin infusion process. The resultant

composite was subjected to an impact of 2.7J, using a Davenport non-instrumented falling-dart impact tower. The resultant delamination area was photographed using transmitted light and a fixed magnification. The composite was then subjected to a healing cycle, with the photography being repeated to compare the damage area.

RESULTS

Resin Testing

Results from the compact tension test are shown in Figure 2a and b, showing the relative load to failure and extension to failure respectively for the materials after 5 different healing cycles. The data is all referenced to the properties of the initial unmodified resin system, showing the effect of adding the healing agent on the mechanical properties of the resin both before and after healing.

In Figure 2a, in the first instance, it can be seen that the addition of the healing agent has caused a 25% drop in the load to failure that is measured for the samples in original condition. However, upon application of a healing cycle at 100°C, there is a clear advantage gained by the modified system, as it recovers 30% of its original load to failure, compared with around 2% recovery for the reference resin system. This trend continues with successive increases in the healing temperature, until a healing cycle at 140°C leads to a recovery of 50% of the original load to failure in the modified resin, but under 5% in the reference system. In all cases, the scatter in the data was inconsequential, being below the difference between neighbouring curves.

Figure 2b shows a similar trend, however the addition of the healing agent increases the extension to failure of the modified resin to above that of the reference resin. Also, it can be seen that the percentage recovery is much more dramatic, culminating in that obtained at 140°C which exceeded that of the unfractured modified resin sample by over 20%.

Both of the results shown in Figure 1 can be explained by assuming that addition of the thermoplastic alters the mechanical properties of the reference resin such that the modified resin is plasticized. Hence the observation of greater extension to failure and decreased load to failure for this system, which can be assumed to have a lower elastic modulus than the reference resin.

Repeated healing is also illustrated on these graphs, as each point is derived from the fracture of three specimens, three times at each condition. The data therefore represents approximately 20 healings of any one specimen. No degradation of healing performance was observed during this time, with the results for the healing at 140°C being obtained among the last of the test data.

Using BS 13586:2000, it was possible to calculate the critical stress concentration factor and critical strain energy release rate for each resin under each healing condition. The results are shown in Figure 3a and b respectively. It can be seen that the results follow the general trend of those shown in Figure 2a, with the precise degree of recovery being slightly better in terms of the critical strain energy release rate than it is for the critical stress concentration factor.

From all of these results, it is readily apparent that the modified healing resin recovers significantly more of its mechanical properties after an appropriate healing cycle than does the reference resin system. In fact, from these data it is apparent that following a healing cycle of

140°C for 90 minutes, between 50 and 70% of the original mechanical properties of the unmodified resin can be recovered, suggesting that significant healing of composite materials using this as the matrix resin should be possible.

a.

b.

Figure 2. Results from the compact tension testing showing a. the relative load to failure of the two resins before and after a variety of healing cycles; and b. the relative extension to failure of the two resins under the same conditions.

a.

b.

Figure 3. Results of data reduction showing a. the relative critical stress concentration factor of the two resins before and after a variety of healing cycles; and b. the relative critical strain energy release rate of the two resins under the same conditions.

Composite Testing

Glass fibre composites were manufactured by filament winding, with glass-fibres being chosen to enable the damage to be assessed using transmitted light rather than x-ray analysis or ultrasonic inspection. Once produced, small impact panels measuring 10*10 cm were cut from the panels and impacted with an energy of 2.7 J. Photographs of the damage were taken,

with a typical example being shown in Figure 4a. The panel was then subjected to a healing cycle at 130°C for 1 hour, the result being shown in Figure 4b. Image analysis was used to measure the change in area upon healing, which showed that there was a reduction of greater than 30% on average in the observed damage area. It is also readily apparent that matrix cracking that is visible in the original photograph could not be observed in the one taken post-healing.

Figure 4. Photographs showing an example of a glass-fibre composite panel impacted at 2.7 J a: before and b: after a healing cycle. The presence of delamination and matrix cracking can readily be observed in a, while the area is reduced and the matrix cracks eliminated in b.

Again healing has been shown to be achievable, this time in composites. However, to date, no results on recovery of mechanical properties have been obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

A modified resin system that is capable of undergoing a healing process upon fracture has been demonstrated.

This resin system, as it is based on conventional epoxy resin technology, is particularly suitable for use in the manufacture of composite materials.

As it undergoes conventional cure, and does not require the inclusion of any second-phase materials, it is amenable to conventional wet lay-up and vacuum-bag processing techniques.

The nature of the resin system means that the healing agent is distributed throughout the matrix so that a crack occurring anywhere within the structure can be healed effectively.

This resin system was tested using compact-tension specimens, and shown to be capable of recovering up to 70% of the virgin fracture toughness on application of an optimised healing cycle, which did not entail the addition of any further material.

Manufacture of composite panels was demonstrated, and a reduction in damage zone size and elimination of matrix cracking showed that the system was capable of visibly reducing the severity of impact damage.

Further mechanical testing results on the resin and the composite are required, and alternative resin systems are also under development.

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